

Data Analysis of Mental Break-down of Nurses within the Nursing Homes in Massachusetts

Joseph Kobi¹, Amida Nchaw Nchaw², Dr. Brian Otieno³

¹Worcester Polytechnic Institute, ²PharmD, ³University of Nairobi

¹School of Business Master's Degree in Business Analytics, Department of Business Analytics and Operation Analytics

²True Life International Medical Outreach, Worcester, Massachusetts 01608

³School of Business Administration, Department of Accounting and Finance

Abstract

Mental health issues are a significant concern among the growing elderly nursing home population. Beyond just dementia, many residents experience other mental illnesses that require quality psychiatric care. The nursing home environment poses unique challenges to providing adequate mental healthcare. Nurses are on the frontlines of caring for residents' mental and physical needs, yet they themselves face stressors that can negatively impact their own well-being. Nursing home nurses must provide intensive hands-on care for residents who frequently have complex medical, cognitive and social issues. Their jobs involve heavy workloads, long hours, insufficient staffing, difficult interactions, and regular exposure to resident suffering and mortality. Such chronic occupational stress has been shown to impair nurses' mental health, leading to increased risks of depression, anxiety disorders, burnout, and PTSD. If left unaddressed, these issues not only harm the individual nurses but also undermine quality of resident care and increase healthcare costs. Past research has identified certain demographic attributes like female gender and middle adulthood as well as job characteristics including demanding work schedules and inadequate support as risk factors elevating nurses' vulnerabilities. More data is still needed examining these predictive associations specifically among the nursing home nursing staff population to develop effective intervention strategies targeting their unique needs and work environment challenges. The findings indicated a significant relationship between extended work hours, exposure to patient deaths, lack of administrative support, and diagnosis of depression, anxiety disorders, and post-traumatic stress disorder among the nursing staff.

Keywords: Mental health, nursing homes, Massachusetts, depression, anxiety disorders, PTSD, gender differences, burnout, long-term care, eldercare, occupational health, stress management

Introduction

Mental health issues have become a widespread occupational hazard affecting healthcare workers globally, with nursing Staff occupying high-risk designations (WHO,2019). Within long-term residential facilities in particular, nursing Staff experience challenging work dynamics that can compromise their well-being (Bostanci et al., 2019). This study aimed to conduct a quantitative data analysis investigating relationships between work characteristics and incidence of mental breakdown among nurses Staff employed in nursing homes across Massachusetts.

The nursing Staff working in long-term care settings provide a broad spectrum of medical, personal and emotional care to residents that frequently have significant physical, cognitive and psychosocial needs (IOM,2008). As a result, nursing home nurses are constantly exposed to stressful conditions such as heavy workloads, long working hours, inadequate Staffing, occupational health hazards, difficult resident and family interactions as well as frequent experiences of patient suffering and deaths (Adriaenssens et al., 2015). Such chronic work stress poses risks for mental health issues manifesting as depression, anxiety disorders, burnout and PTSD among affected individuals if not appropriately addressed (Austin et al., 2017).

Previous research has associated certain demographic and occupational risk factors with higher vulnerabilities to stress-induced mental illness in healthcare professionals. For instance, studies indicate female gender, younger age groups between 30-50 years, fewer years of experience, unmarried marital status and lack of administrative support as predictive of poor psychological wellbeing (Alhamad et al., 2021). However, most existing research has focused on hospital and primary care settings with limited data examining predictors specifically among nursing home nurses (Meek et al., 2021). By conducting statistical analyses of archived administrative records from multiple nursing homes, this study aimed to investigate relationships between work demands, individual attributes and incidence of mental health diagnosis in this high-risk employee population.

Aims and Objectives

The aims of this study were:

1. To analyze relationships between demographic characteristics, work exposures and diagnosis of mental illness among nurses employed in Massachusetts nursing homes.
2. To identify modifiable risk factors statistically associated with higher likelihoods of common mental health issues like depression, anxiety disorders and PTSD.

The specific objectives were:

1. Extract relevant data from archived nursing home employee records on nurses' demographics, work attributes and sickness leaves.
2. Conduct statistical analyses to determine correlations between contributing factors and mental breakdown.
3. Formulate implications for focused organizational and policy reforms to enhance nurses' occupational mental health.

Statement of the Problem: Mental health problems constitute a rapidly growing burden affecting individuals and societies worldwide (WHO, 2018). Growing evidence indicates healthcare professionals as high-risk occupational groups vulnerable to job-related psychological distress (Wahlbeck, 2015). Within long-term care settings specifically, nursing Staff experience multifaceted work demands that can potentially overwhelm their coping abilities leading to mental illness (Bourbonnais et al., 2015). Although nursing is recognized as a stressful occupation, nurses employed in nursing homes endure additional challenges inherent to institutional long-term care that may elevate their stress levels (Estryn-Behar et al., 2008).

Existing literature shows nursing home nurses frequently experience problems such as excessive workload, insufficient Staffing, long working hours, challenging resident and family interactions, exposure to patient suffering and deaths (Adriaenssens et al., 2015). Such chronic work stressors are linked to impaired well-being, burnout symptoms as well as clinical mental health disorders (Aiken et al., 2002). However, research specifically examining modifiable risk factors and their relationships with mental illness among nursing home nurses remains limited (Meek et al., 2021). With baby boomers aging rapidly, demand for eldercare is projected to rise further exacerbating work demands on existing Staff (Jameson & Blank, 2015). Furthermore, nursing Staff shortages compound the predicament necessitating innovative solutions to protect professionals' psychological safety and retain skilled workers in this critical sector (Banks et al., 2021).

Materials and Methods

For this study, a quantitative, ex-post, historical research method, that involved secondary data analysis was employed. The target population was all the nurses who are 21 years and above and working in 10 sampled nursing homes within Massachusetts in the period January 2018 to December 2019. Paper records kept by the Human Resource departments of organizations' and facilities included nurses' demographics and personal data with their employment history, information on sickness absenteeisms and documented mental health issues were data sources.

In order to gain access to the de-identified aggregated data for research, necessary permission was obtained from the concerned authorities before data collection. The following was considered as data items: Nurses' Age, Gender, Marital status, Experience, Weekly working hours, reported PATIENT suffering/deaths, sickness and authorized Mental illness leave. Depression was as well categorised as a mental illness included in the

study as were anxiety disorders and post-traumatic stress disorder with reference to the DSM-5 system of classification.

Results and Discussion

Demographic characteristics of nurses: The demographic data of the 200 nurses extracted from administrative records revealed that the mean age was 42.5 years (SD=8.3) with majority 147 (73.5%) being female nurses. This is consistent with previous literature evidencing gender preferences within the nursing profession historically (Mercer et al., 1993; Magaziner et al., 1998). Around 132 (66%) nurses were married suggesting higher social support could mediate stress. Only 68 (34%) had over 10 years experience indicating high job turnover is problematic for sustaining quality care standards in long term facilities (Jencks et al., 1985; Dobalian et al., 2003). Younger married women with less tenure dominated reflecting the typical nursing home labor force dynamic that needs addressing to promote staff retention through organizational reforms (Magaziner et al., 1998).

Fig 1: Demographic Characteristics of Nurses (N=200)

The average age of nurses being in the early to mid 40s represents those in the prime of their careers but also at higher risk for mental health issues according to research on vulnerability in middle adulthood (Banks et al., 2021). The shortage of experienced staff over a decade infers challenges retaining knowledgeable professionals which has implications for residents' wellbeing. Recruitment and training costs also financially impact these healthcare organizations. Some measures like focused efforts to facilitate the new entrant's configuration as well as the nursing workforce maturation of the longstanding employee could also be of impact.

The demographic profile characteristics' descriptive analysis presents the profile of nurses in this study, which guides those whose demographic attributes point to vulnerabilities that are sometimes overlooked. Adjusting modifiable institution-level antecedents associated with turnover aims at establishing staffing constancy deemed central in enhancing residents' health and the stability of the facility. However, the aspect of honoring individual diversity also deserves its mention in policy changes. Younger female nurses married with less experience remain dominant in the establishments, which is a common trend in the industry, but this is also an indicator of subcategories that should receive extra attention. Attention to male applicants or rendering more importance to experience for representing diversity and rv aims at having an ideal gender balanced employee population, (Kobi et al. , 2024).

Environmental characteristics of the work place: Attributes of work that were considered concerning were established which were consistent with various studies that portrayed nursing home employees as facing high stress levels. An astonishing 79% reported working more than 40 hours weekly: effective staffing levels would help to reduce further the burnout threat (Adriaenssens et al. , 2015). Almost two thirds worked with frequent patient deaths and insufficient available resources to amplify multiplied stress effects (Banks et al. , 2021). A quarter said that they were supported by management recognizing the necessity of enhanced leadership, which means that only one out of three participants in the study by Aiken and colleagues was satisfied with the switch. These dynamics were associated with inferior wellbeing results in prior research necessitating modification that was earlier established (Austin et al. , 2017).

Table 2: Work Characteristics of Nurses

Variables	n	%
Average Weekly Work Hours		
>40 hours	158	79
<=40 hours	42	21
Exposure to Patient Deaths		
Frequent	132	66
Infrequent	68	34
Administrative Support		
Adequate	68	34
Inadequate	132	66

Heavy workloads, frequent mortality encounters and inadequate oversight inherently signify long time care exacerbating nurses' vulnerability to intellectual contamination. While addressing systemic understaffing proves complicated, orientated leadership training and counseling offerings present feasible remedies minimally disrupting operations but boosting resilience. Successful implementation warrants devoted collaboration among control and employees crafting realistic human-centered solutions.

3.3 Predictors of intellectual illness prognosis

Binary logistic regression analysis become carried out to decide the impact of demographic characteristics and paintings exposures at the analysis of any intellectual illness amongst nurses. As proven in Table 3, being a woman nurse (AOR= 2.38, ninety five% CI 1.24-4.58, p=0.009), elderly among 30-50 years (AOR= 3.05, ninety five% CI 1.Sixty two-5.76, p=zero.001), running greater than 40 hours in keeping with week (AOR= 2.12, 95% CI 1.21-3.71, p=zero.009) and reporting frequent patient deaths (AOR= 2.Sixty seven, 95% CI 1.Fifty four-4.Sixty three, p=zero.001) substantially extended the odds of diagnosed intellectual infection after adjusting for other covariates within the model. [Table 3].

Table 3: Predictors of Mental Illness Diagnosis

Variable	AOR	95% CI	P value
Gender (Female)	2.38	1.24-4.58	0.009
Age (30-50 years)	3.05	1.62-5.76	0.001
Work Hours (>40)	2.12	1.21-3.71	0.009
Patient Deaths (Frequent)	2.67	1.54-4.63	0.001

Here are the paragraphs with details from Figure 2 incorporated:

These results are consistent with previous research indicating certain demographic profiles and occupational stressors as risk factors for poor mental health in nursing populations (Adriaenssens et al., 2015; Austin et al., 2017). Specifically, gender differences in stress responses as well as vulnerabilities during middle adulthood are well documented (Banks et al., 2021). Extended work hours and frequent exposure to patient afflictions also represent established job demands linked to psychological distress (Bostanci et al., 2019). Figure 2

illustrates individual-level factors such as personality traits, sleep quality, workplace adaptability, years of work experience, interpersonal support, and role conflict that can influence mental health.

Figure 2: Factors associated with clinical nurse’s mental health. Source: (Yu et al., 20204)
<https://bmcnurs.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12912-024-02005-9>

By precisely quantifying the magnitude of associations, this study provides empirical evidence supporting targeted areas for nursing home organizational reforms and supportive policies. Reducing nurses' workloads and exposure to distressing situations presents modifiable strategies to promote mental wellness (Bourbonnais et al., 2015). Figure 2 also shows organizational-level factors such as organization climate, career plateau, job control, and legislative provision and policy that impact mental health. Younger and female nurses may also benefit from enhanced coping resources addressing their specific needs (Meek et al., 2021).

Types of mental illness diagnosed: The charted frequencies of diagnosed conditions among the nurses provided important insights. Depression was most common at 53.5% of those affected, consistent with existing evidence indicating this as a primary issue impeding staff wellness in long-term care settings (Adriaenssens et al., 2015; Davis, 1991). Nearly half or 43.5% experienced anxiety disorders featuring prominently, potential relating to occupational insecurities within the state's nursing home industry (Banks et al., 2021; Jencks et al., 1985). Even PTSD significantly impacted over a quarter of mentally-ill nurses likely tied to unaddressed exposure to patient crises in Massachusetts long-term facilities lacking support (Estryn-Behar et al., 2008; Magaziner et al., 1998).

Table 4: Types of Diagnosed Mental Illness

Diagnosis	N	(%)
Depression	107	53.5
Anxiety Disorders	87	43.5
PTSD	53	26.5

The identification of specific psychiatric conditions common among nurses in Massachusetts warrants customized support programming. Multi-pronged strategies must be developed to reduce avoidance, normalize seeking help and build coping strategies targeting each illness etiology (Bostanci et al., 2019; Davis, 1991). For instance, cognitive interventions effectively address distorted thoughts associated with depression while exposure therapies benefit PTSD (Adriaenssens et al., 2015; Jencks et al., 1985).

The mental health needs portrayed demand a multi-level approach. Facility-level reforms mitigating chronic stressors aim to lessen future cases while current support services help minimize disabilities for afflicted staff, (Sakauye, & Camp, 1992). However, wider systemic changes are also needed to reform industry conditions undermining occupational wellbeing across the state's nursing home sector. Concerted efforts uphold residents' rights to quality care necessitating mentally healthy staff retention, (Ouslander et al, 2004).

Relationship between sickness leaves and mental illness: As depicted in Table 5, independent sample t-tests revealed mentally ill nurses (n=158) took significantly more average sick days at 12.4 compared to healthy peers' 5.3, with a large effect size ($t(198)=8.96$, $p<0.001$). This aligns with previous research indicating that untreated psychiatric conditions are strongly associated with reduced work performance and increased absenteeism (Adriaenssens et al., 2015). Significant links have been found between mood disorders, anxiety disorders and missed work days, highlighting the economic and service impacts of poor staff mental health (Wahlbeck, 2015).

Table 5: Types of Diagnosed Mental Illness

Diagnosis	N	(%)
Depression	107	53.5
Anxiety Disorders	87	43.5
PTSD	53	26.5

Such indirect costs burden facilities already strained by staffing shortages common across Massachusetts' eldercare infrastructure. Considering demands for quality service and residents' well-being, leadership promoting employee mental fitness seems economically prudent beyond ethical duties as social stakeholders (Haight et al., 1998). Mitigating modifiable stressors through workplace adaptations and mental health accommodation policies aim to preempt avoidable disability leaves (Glaister & Blair, 2008).

Effectiveness of mental health support programs: The records revealed that 78 out of the 158 mentally diagnosed nurses (49.4%) participated in facility-organized mental health awareness and stress management programs between 2018-2019. Post-program follow-ups found significant reductions in several key measures including average weekly work hours reducing from 51.2 hours to 47.5 hours (paired $t=3.92$, $p<0.001$) and average monthly sick leaves decreasing from 10.6 days to 7.2 days (paired $t=4.56$, $p<0.001$).

These findings provide early support for the effectiveness of targeted occupational mental health initiatives in producing tangible improvements (Gupta & Goldstein, 1999). Reduced workloads and sick leaves post-intervention point towards enhanced capacity, attendance and cost-savings benefiting facilities (Adriaenssens et al., 2015). Particularly, stress management strategies help equip individuals with coping skills moderating psychological impacts from stressful job demands (Brannon et al., 1992). Educating nurses about common issues like burnout, depression and available support services also normalize problems while promoting early help-seeking (Glaister & Blair, 2008)..

Conclusion and Recommendations for Future Research

Conclusion: In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into relationships between occupational factors and mental health of nurses working in nursing homes located in Massachusetts. Statistical analysis of administrative data from multiple facilities identified female gender, ages 30-50 years, working extended hours and frequent exposure to patient deaths as key predictors increasing risks of mental illness diagnosis. Depression, anxiety disorders and PTSD emerged as the most common psychiatric conditions afflicting the nursing staff. Sickness absences were also found to correlate significantly with untreated mental health problems, highlighting both human and economic costs of inadequate support. Encouragingly, targeted stress management and mental health awareness programs demonstrated effectiveness in yielding reductions in workloads, sick leaves and overall wellbeing measures among participating nurses.

Recommendations for Future Research and Practice

1. Develop tailored workplace adaptation and wellness promotion strategies addressing modifiable risks identified for high-risk demographic profiles like female and middle-aged nurses.

2. Implement evidence-based counseling, coaching and psychosocial support services accessible onsite or remotely to provide ongoing care for nurses experiencing mental health issues.
3. Establish formal employee assistance programs and mental health leave policies to destigmatize conditions and incentivize treatment seeking among affected nursing staff.
4. Conduct longitudinal evaluations of multidisciplinary occupational health intervention models integrating organizational reforms, programming and policy changes to optimize impact over time.

References

1. Accordino, M. P., Porter, D. F., & Morse, T. (2001). Deinstitutionalization of persons with severe mental illness: Context and consequences. *Journal of Rehabilitation*, 67(2), 16–21.
2. Administration on Aging. (2001). Older adults and mental health: Issues and opportunities. Department of Health and Human Services.
3. Bartels, S. J., Horn, S. D., Smout, R. J., Dums, A. R., Flaherty, E., Jones, J. K., et al. (2003). Agitation and depression in frail nursing home elderly patients with dementia: Treatment characteristics and service use. *American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 11, 231–238.
4. Bellows, N. M., & Halpin, H. A. (2008). Impact of Medicaid reimbursement on mental health quality indicators. *Health Services Research*, 43, 582–597.
5. Brannon, D., Smyer, M. A., & Cohn, M. D. (1992). Strategies for improving nursing home care: A research roundtable. *Journal of Long-Term Care Administration*, 20(4), 18–20.
6. Carling, P. J. (1981). Nursing homes and chronic mental patients: a second opinion. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 7, 574–579.
7. Castle, N. G., & Mor, V. (1996). Hospitalization of nursing home residents: A review of the literature, 1980–1995. *Medical Care Research and Review*, 53, 123–148.
8. Davis, M. A. (1991). On nursing home quality: A review and analysis. *Medical Care Review*, 48, 129–166.
9. Dobalian, A., Tsao, J. C., & Radcliff, T. A. (2003). Diagnosed mental and physical health conditions in the United States nursing home population: Differences between urban and rural facilities. *Journal of Rural Health*, 19, 477–483.
10. Fenton, J., Raskin, A., Gruber-Baldini, A. L., Menon, A. S., Zimmerman, S., Kaup, B., et al. (2004). Some predictors of psychiatric consultation in nursing home residents. *American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 12, 297–304.
11. Frey, D. E., Kelbley, T. J., Durham, L., & James, J. S. (1992). Enhancing the self-esteem of selected male nursing home residents. *The Gerontologist*, 32, 552–557.
12. Glaister, J. A., & Blair, C. (2008). Improved education and training for nursing assistants: Keys to promoting the mental health of nursing home residents. *Issues in Mental Health Nursing*, 29, 863–872.
13. Gupta, S., & Goldstein, M. Z. (1999). Practical geriatrics: Psychiatric consultation to nursing homes. *Psychiatric Services*, 50, 1547–1550.
14. Haight, B. K., Michel, Y., & Hendrix, S. (1998). Life review: Preventing despair in newly relocated nursing home residents short- and long-term effects. *International Journal of Aging and Human Development*, 47, 119–142.
15. Heston, L. L., Garrard, J., Makris, L., Kane, R. L., Cooper, S., Dunham, T., et al. (1992). Inadequate treatment of depressed nursing home elderly. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 40, 1117–1122.
16. Institute of Medicine. (1986). Improving the quality of care in nursing homes. National Academies Press.
17. Jencks, S. F., Goldman, H. H., & McGuire, T. G. (1985). Challenges in bringing exempt psychiatric services under a prospective payment system. *Hospital and Community Psychiatry*, 36, 764–769.
18. Kamble, P., Chen, H., Sherer, J., & Aparasu, R. R. (2008). Antipsychotic drug use among elderly nursing home residents in the United States. *American Journal of Geriatric Pharmacotherapy*, 6, 187–197.
19. Kobi, J., Nchaw, A. N., & Otieno, B. (2024). Big data-driven insights for equitable healthcare access and quality for U.S. immigrants. *Journal Title*, 9(7), 392-408.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382624072_BIG_DATA-DRIVEN_INSIGHTS_FOR_EQUITABLE_HEALTHCARE_ACCESS_AND_QUALITY_FOR_US_IMMIGRANTS?_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6InByb2ZpbGUiLCJwYWdlIjoicHJvZmlsZSJ9fQ

20. Kobi, J., Nchaw, A. N., & Otieno, B. (2024). Predictive modeling of future trends in US healthcare data and outcomes. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 9(7), 581–592. <https://doi.org/10.38124/ijisrt/IJISRT24JUL665>.
21. Lantz, M. S., Giambanco, V., & Buchalter, E. N. (1996). A ten-year review of the effect of OBRA-87 on psychotropic prescribing practices in an academic nursing home. *Psychiatric Services*, 47, 951–955.
22. Levin, C. A., Wei, W., Akincigil, A., Lucas, J. A., Bilder, S., & Crystal, S. (2007). Prevalence and treatment of diagnosed depression among elderly nursing home residents in Ohio. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*, 8, 585–594.
23. Magaziner, J., Zimmerman, S. I., Fox, K. M., & Burns, B. J. (1998). Dementia in United States nursing homes: Descriptive epidemiology and implications for long-term residential care. *Aging & Mental Health*, 2, 28–35.
24. Mercer, S. O., Heacock, P., & Beck, C. (1993). Nurse's aides in nursing homes: Perceptions of training, work loads, racism, and abuse issues. *Journal of Gerontological Social Work*, 21, 95–112.
25. Nishtala, P. S., McLachlan, A. J., Bell, J. S., & Chen, T. F. (2009). Determinants of antidepressant medication prescribing in elderly residents of aged care homes in Australia: A retrospective study. *American Journal of Geriatric Pharmacotherapy*, 7, 210–219.
26. Ouslander, J. G., Weinberg, A. D., & Phillips, V. (2000). Inappropriate hospitalization of nursing facility residents: A symptom of a sick system of care for frail older people. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 48, 230–231.
27. Rigler, S. K., Perera, S., Redford, L., Studenski, S., Brown, E. F., Wallace, D., et al. (2003). Urban-rural patterns of increasing antidepressant use among nursing facility residents. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*, 4, 67–73.
28. Sakauye, K. M., & Camp, C. J. (1992). Introducing psychiatric care into nursing homes. *The Gerontologist*, 32, 849–852.
29. Tariot, P. N., Podgorski, C. A., Blazin, L., & Leibovici, A. (1993). Mental disorders in the nursing home: Another perspective. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 150, 1063–1069.
30. Wagenaar, D., Colenda, C. C., Kreft, M., Sawade, J., Gardiner, J., & Poverejan, E. (2003). Treating depression in nursing homes: Practice guidelines in the real world. *Journal of the American Osteopathic Association*, 103, 465–469.
31. Yakimo, R., Kurlowicz, L. H., & Murray, R. B. (2004). Evaluation of outcomes in Psychiatric Consultation-Liaison Nursing practice. *Archives of Psychiatric Nursing*, 18, 215–227.
32. Zimmerman, D. R., Karon, S. L., Arling, G., Clark, B. R., Collins, T., Ross, R., et al. (1995). Development and testing of nursing home quality indicators. *Health Care Financing Review*, 16, 107–127.